

Environment and sustainability – studying Green Area Index - (IAV) - Neighborhood and Environment and health – arboviruses in the context of my neighborhood.

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Maria Celeste Souza de Castro,
Jéssica Libório
Robson Souza,
Fabiana M. Esteves, – Mathematics ;
Keitiane da Costa Pimenta -Chemical,
Vanilton Miranda Nunes- Biology
Camila Brito - Scientific Initiation

Abstract: This pedagogical practice within the scope of the Connect Project, reports an open schooling initiative that was developed at the Senhor do Bonfim State College (CESB) and involved subjects in the area of Science and Mathematics, having as participants in the action students of basic education, guided by the teachers of the Senhor do Bonfim State College (CESB): Maria Celeste Souza de Castro, Robson Souza, Fabiana M. Esteves, Keitiane da Costa Pimenta and Vanilton Miranda Nunes . In partnership with the State University of Bahia (UNEB), through the Research Group on Management, Education, Science and Technologies for Social Inclusion (GEC & TIS), part of the Multidisciplinary and Multi-Institutional Graduate Program in Knowledge Dissemination (PPGDC) and the Green School Program (PEV) of the Federal University of Vale do São Francisco (UNIVASF-Petrolina).

1. INTRODUCTION:

The meaning of this partnership was the implementation of open schooling, applying the Care-Know-Do methodology, from Connect, articulated with the doctoral research of Professor Maria Celeste Souza de Castro, under the guidance of Professor Silvar Ferreira Ribeiro, who sought to develop collaborative actions in which it was possible to expand the universe of references of students from a scientific look at the reality in which they are inserted. using the language of science and mathematics to critically understand their context, increasing their scientific capital. With this intent, a CESB

Collaboration Network (RC) was built in which there was integration and mutual help of the following actors: teachers and students of the 2nd Teaching classes of CESB, students of the degrees in Mathematics and Physics and researchers of GEC&TIS.

Assuming the principle of inseparability and interdisciplinarity, the students involved were encouraged to use the contents worked on in the disciplines to 'look' critically at the context in which they were inserted, to build a formative path based on their identification with the themes worked on and to produce material and disseminate knowledge to their communities.

2. PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

The studies were carried out based on the challenges of the students' reality in which **the pillars of CONNECT** subsidized the actions. The pillars adopted were **OPEN SCHOOLING**, due to the idea that the expansion of the study of disciplinary contents based on the exploration of its own context would enable a more interactive and flexible learning environment; **SCIENCE-ACTION**, considering that the themes IAV-Neighborhood and Arboviroses- 'Aedes in focus' were worked on from the perspective that students could disseminate the knowledge acquired through the awareness of their families and the community of their neighborhood.

Figure 01: Project implementation

For each theme, a question has been constructed.

For the Theme, (IAV) - Neighborhood: What is the Green Area Index (IAV) of my neighborhood? What is the importance of maintaining green areas in the neighborhood? And what Public Policy can we suggest to the rulers of our city?

For the theme: Environment and health – the arboviruses "Aedes in focus", the question: What environmental awareness do students, their families and friends in the neighborhood have regarding the care of the environment to prevent the proliferation of the Aedes mosquito? What can be done to increase environmental awareness in your community?

Figure 02: Data Survey

The

methodological steps that support the CONNECT (Care-Know-Do) proposal were used. In an interdisciplinary action, the themes, environment and health, transversalized the discussions of the following disciplines: Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, Biology and Scientific Initiation (CI). The stage of work with the contents, conservation of fauna and flora, impact of environmental degradation and low green area index (IAV) on the proliferation of mosquitoes; care for the environment - afforestation and sanitation culminated with the study, in the discipline of Mathematics, with the study of Areas, connection with Green Areas (TOLEDO; MAZZEI AND SANTOS, 2009); function study, making a connection with the theme conscious consumption of water (BONJORNO, et. Al. 2020) and the contents of Statistics to study the arboviruses of 'my neighborhood' in a proposition of knowing, intervening and disseminating.

Students from the 2nd High School/Integral School were involved in the actions, totaling 97 students. Of the community actions, seven neighborhoods were affected, considered as neighborhoods that have social vulnerability.

2.2.KNOW STAGE

In the "Aedes in Focus" Project, the areas of Natural Sciences and Mathematics were involved.

Figure 03: Use of mathematics to calculate the green area index

In mathematics, the contents of Statistics were studied, seeking to enable students to critically interpret the environmental situations in their communities, through the analysis of the graphs. We understand that this action developed the competence to use mathematical language to build consistent argumentation and present proposals to the community using collected data. In chemistry, the students worked on the following guiding questions: the use of insecticides (the smoke cars), the damage caused to the environment. In the Scientific Initiation (CI) course, students were encouraged to build hypotheses, study objectives, data collection and compilation.

In the Green Areas Index (IAV)-Bairro Project, the content worked on was Geometry: Areas and Perimeter. Using Google Earth tools to capture photos and the cell phone itself to take photos of the neighbourhood, of Excel for the organization of the collected data and of the textbook for the study of the content. From these, Power Point presentations and videos were produced.

The results of the work were exhibited in the classroom, through oral presentations and in the final action of the Unit, with dissemination on the murals of the schoolyard.

Figure 04: Students using Google Earth tools

2.3.DO STAGE

At the end, the students prepared videos, a promotional card and posters.

With the encouragement of developing collaborative actions, the high school/full-time students worked together with the students of the universities involved - UNEB and UNIVASF - Petrolina - PEV Project. The video, produced by student Felipe Rodrigues da Silva, presented data about the neighborhood in which he lives and reflected on the need for Public Policies for the conservation and expansion of green areas. This work was built collectively among colleagues and with the help of the resident of the neighborhood Mr. Jailson Araújo Presentations were also built, using the Power Poin

Figure 05: Poster

3. FINDINGS RELATED TO THE OPEN EDUCATION APPROACH

The pillars of CONNECT: OPEN SCHOOLING and SCIENCE-ACTION allowed all those involved to develop their actions in a flexible way (the action was developed without charging for embedded results) in which each teacher could follow a methodology that resulted in the binomial SCIENCE-ACTION, that is, to bring together the scientific concepts, worked on the contents, and action in their reality (spreading knowledge and information). It is also worth noting that the students of the school were protagonists in their actions. We can consider that working with this idea is challenging because it takes us out of the 'boxes' and puts us in front of a greater involvement with the social issues of these students.

"This science action was selected by the government of Bahia because it is relevant to the population of the state. The mapping of green areas as a law to be discussed and approved will benefit the entire region in the area of health and environment. In addition, in the educational area, the law will facilitate public education policies also because this initiative was the result of the CARE-KNOW-DO open schooling of the CONNECT project supported by UNEB

This model can be promising in implementing the idea of "Comprehensive School" in a format that breaks with the idea of components distributed in one school day.

4. STUDENT RESULTS

The students produced promotional material, built texts with reflections on the themes and solved questions with the themes and contents studied. I understand that there was a greater involvement of the students during the period in which the projects were being developed

At the end of the school year, the students of the 2nd B reflected on the motivation they had to study mathematics subjects thinking about the issues of their own lives and their living spaces.

Figure 06: The student Jessica Libório was one of the 63 young people selected to attend the deputy/senate event for discussion of the new public law "mapping green areas" which was a project developed with the CONNECT open schooling CARE-KNOW-DO approach.

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